

Appendix S2: Hill numbers profiles of Gamma diversity (site comparisons)

Fractal sampling design reveals climate and scale effects on rainforest bird communities in central Africa

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Appendix S2 presents coverage-based diversity profiles, asymptotic estimates, rarefaction/extrapolation curves, and evenness profiles derived from Hill numbers ($q = 0, 1, 2$) for gamma diversity (site-level). These visual summaries describe how sampling completeness, richness, and evenness vary across sampling scenarios and along the rainfall gradient.

Table S1. Sample coverage at the point-count (alpha plot) level

Summary of sample coverage (SC) for bird communities at the alpha-plot (point-count) level ($n = 144$ plots). Coverage is reported for two scenarios: (i) at the observed sample size (maximum number of individuals detected per plot), and (ii) at a common standardized sample size ($m = 52$ individuals), corresponding to the minimum maximum sample size across plots. SC values closer to 1 indicate more complete sampling.

Scenario	Number of alpha plots (point counts)	Mean sample coverage	SD	Minimum	Maximum	% plots < 0.70	% plots < 0.80
Observed sample size (max m per plot)	144	0.646	0.154	0.172	0.932	57.639	86.111
Common sample size across plots ($m = 52$)	144	0.448	0.101	0.136	0.677	100.0	100.0

Table S2 Summary statistics of alpha-level Hill numbers ($q = 0$) estimated using size-based and coverage-based standardization

Hill numbers were estimated for individual point counts using size-based standardization at the maximum common number of individuals and coverage-based standardization at a target sample coverage of approximately 0.80. Both approaches yielded nearly identical distributions of richness estimates.

Standardization	Min	1st quartile	Median	Mean	3rd quartile	Max
Size-based (max m)	38.54	52.73	57.81	58.35	63.49	81.99
Coverage-based (SC \approx 0.80)	38.54	52.18	57.54	57.80	63.36	81.99

FIGURE S1: Sample coverage site level using abundance-based estimator
Sample coverage was estimated at the site level using the Good–Turing frequency–based

estimators of Chiu et al. (2023). Curves show sample coverage as a function of the cumulative number of point counts (sampling units) within each forest site.

A. Coverage and completeness profiles (site-level: gamma diversity) (Figures S2–S9)

These figures illustrate the sample completeness and coverage profiles for bird communities across the full dataset and the different sampling scenarios (triads) for Gamma diversity (site-

level). The curves show the relationship between sample coverage and diversity order ($q = 0, 1, 2$), with higher completeness values indicating greater sampling representativeness. This allows visual comparison of data completeness among sites and scales.

FIGURE S2 Coverage-based sampling curve (full sampling scenario, n=144 alpha plots)

FIGURE S3 Coverage-based sampling curve (third triad scenario, n=108 alpha plots)

FIGURE S4 Coverage-based sampling curve (second triad scenario, n=36 alpha plots)

FIGURE S5 Coverage-based sampling curve (first triad scenario, n=12 alpha plots)

FIGURE S6 Sample completeness curve (full sampling scenario, n=144 alpha plots)

FIGURE S7 Sample completeness curve (third triad scenario, n=108 alpha plots)

FIGURE S8 Sample completeness curve (second triad scenario, n=36 alpha plots)

FIGURE S9 Sample completeness curve (First triad scenario, n=12 alpha plots)

B Asymptotic diversity profiles (gamma diversity, site-level) (Figures S10–S13)

Asymptotic diversity profiles present the estimated asymptotic Hill numbers ($q = 0, 1, 2$) across sampling scenarios at the site level (gamma), showing the effective number of species expected under complete sampling. These figures help visualize differences in asymptotic richness, Shannon diversity, and Simpson diversity across forest sites and spatial scales.

FIGURE S10 Observed versus Asymptotic curves (full sampling scenario, $n=144$ alpha plots)

FIGURE S11 Observed versus Asymptotic curves (Third triad scenario, n=108 alpha plots)

FIGURE S12 Observed versus Asymptotic curves (second triad scenario, n=36 alpha plots)

FIGURE S13 Observed versus Asymptotic curves (first triad scenario, n=12 alpha plots)

C. Rarefaction and extrapolation curves (gamma diversity, site-level) (Figures S14–S16)

These figures display the rarefaction and extrapolation curves of Hill numbers ($q = 0, 1, 2$) for each sampling scenario for gamma diversity (site-level). Solid lines represent interpolated (rarefied) values, while dashed lines represent extrapolated values. Shaded areas correspond to 95% confidence intervals. The curves illustrate how diversity accumulates with increasing sample size, allowing standardized comparison among sites and scales. See Chao et al., 2020.

FIGURE S14 Rarefaction-extrapolation curves (third triad scenario, $n=108$ alpha plots)

FIGURE S15 Rarefaction-extrapolation curves (second triad scenario, $n=36$ alpha plots)

FIGURE S16 Rarefaction-extrapolation curves (first triad scenario, n=12 alpha plots)

Evenness profiles (Figures S17–S19)

Evenness profiles illustrate community structure by comparing the relative contributions of common versus rare species across triad levels. Lower slopes indicate higher dominance, whereas flatter profiles suggest more even communities. Together, these patterns provide insights into how spatial scale influences community evenness. See Chao et al., 2020.

FIGURE S17 Evenness profiles curves (third triad, n=108 alpha plots)

FIGURE S18 Evenness profiles curves (second triad, n=36 alpha plots)

FIGURE S19 Evenness profiles curves (first triad, n=12 alpha plots)

